

Tell Me What You've Read and I'll Tell You What You Can Write: Mental Models and Shakespeare's Authorship Question 400 years after the First Folio

Heitor Matallo Junior

Independent Scholar, Campinas, Brazil
Matalloheitor48@gmail.com

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Abstract

This article assumes that the performance of intellectual activities presupposes a corresponding Mental Model. The mental model of a man of letters like Shakespeare is based on his intellectual experience derived from access to libraries and books, attentive reading, experience in the court issues, traveling and mastering languages. The article raises the hypothesis that William of Stratford had a Mental Model as a businessman and not as a man of letters, author of Shakespeare's works. This hypothesis is based on existing information about William's intellectual background, as well as on recently discovered information about his activities as a grain merchant, theater owner and manager. The method used to support my hypothesis is to point out all the possible references contained in Shakespeare's works, showing that William could hardly have had access to these references, as he did not have books, there were no libraries at his disposal and he was not in the habit of reading. Some authors mention that William could have overcome this difficulty through the use of friend's libraries, but there is no indication that this actually happened. The paper also mentions that the most likely candidates for Shakespeare's authorship (Francis Bacon and Edward De Vere) had wide access to books and libraries, intellectual training and the habit of reading and studying, necessary for the formation of the mental model represented in the constructions. Finally, the article concludes that the Mental Model framework can be a complementary and promising tool to help clarify the question of Shakespeare's authorship.

Keywords

Shakespeare authorship, Mental Model,

1. Introduction

The year 2023 marks the 400th anniversary of the publication of what is known as the First Folio, a compilation of 36 plays of William Shakespeare. Celebrated as a world icon of literature, William of Stratford, aroused from the beginning of his career, in the very same year in which he is supposed to have written his first play in 1591/2, a certain doubt about his abilities as a writer. At least that's what Robert Greene (Newcomb, 2004), a well-known poet of the time, expressed.

Coming from an illiterate family with little education, how did William overcome these conditions to become a globally respected writer? How could he form the Mental Model for a high-quality literary production as the one he produced? How could he overcome a mediocre life in the countryside, living in a small village, without having traveled or gaining experience in the Elizabethan court, without having specific knowledge of history, without mastering Latin and Greek, writing about complex political plots, describing scenes in other countries or have an acute vision of English history demonstrated in his plays?

This was the mystery that led to a 400-year distrust of William Shakespeare's true authorship. Who wrote Shakespeare? William of Stratford or someone else? From Robert Greene to the publication of John Thomas Looney's book (Looney, 1920), claiming to have discovered the true Shakespeare in the person of Edward De Vere, there were 350 years of studies, indications of possible candidates (there are already more than 300) and polemics about the real authorship of Shakespeare.

Pieces of evidence were progressively piling up both for and against William of Stratford. Movements in favor of one or another candidate became institutionalized, as there was never a definitive proof to solve the problem. Stratfordians and Oxfordians are still debating and fueling the controversy, which is becoming more and more intense with the use of new computational technologies to identify styles and other small details that may contribute to resolving the dispute.

This paper aims to show that literary activity depends on a corresponding Mental Model. Mental Models are "evolutionary" in the sense that certain cognitive skills are developed with language learning, reading, studying, and obtaining sufficient knowledge to be able to develop the creative faculty. In particular, mastery of the language (in this case, English) is essential. To write with the perfection that can be seen in Shakespeare's plays, it is necessary to master perfectly the English language, rules, syntax and semantics and this cannot be achieved without a process of mental improvement.

I will thus describe through a biographical narrative, schematic in its form, but containing the main elements that may allow to compare Shakespeare's ideal profile with William's real profile. This was, *mutatis mutandis*, the method used by Thomas Henry Smith in his book *Bacon and Shakespeare: A Survey Touching Players, Toys and Writers in the Days of Elisabeth* (Smith, 1857), where he bluntly questions William's authorship of Shakespeare's works and proposes Francis Bacon as the real Shakespeare. It is not my intention to adopt this or that candidate as the pen writer, but to state in general terms the hypothesis that we can have additional evidence of authorship using the idea of the Mental Model.

2. Brief account of the criticism leveled at William of Stratford as an author

At the end of the 16th century, a name emerged in the English literature, destined to become the most renowned figure in world in this field. His name echoes ubiquitously, with countless references to the author's works coming from individuals who may have never read a single line of his plays. The mere mention of his name or one of his works elevates the speaker to a position of linguistic superiority or even that the person has an understanding of significant events in English history, particularly the intricate matters relating to the English court. I am referring to William

Shakespeare (1564 – 1616). His name is so universally recognized, and his fame so overwhelming, that few would dare question his talent. However, considerable controversy surrounds the authorship of the works attributed to this man.

Doubts about William's ability to write such sophisticated plays began in 1592 when Robert Greene (1558 – 1592) (Newcomb, 2004) wrote a pamphlet titled *Groats-Worth of Wit*. As mentioned by Anderson in his excellent book (Anderson, 2011), "*Greene discredits Shakspeare as a writer of any capacity*" and call him as a "*Johannes factotum*" (Anderson, 2011, 31). Further criticism arose in 1600 through an anonymous comedy and also in 1611 with the poet John Davies, who describes William as "both actor and dramatist" and suggests that he was an actor who pretended to be an author " (Anderson, 2011). Perhaps these were the first time that such an allusion about the authorship of Shakespearean plays were made.

The first wave of criticism temporarily ceased with William's death in 1616, and the publication of the First Folio, in 1623. The next 150 years were enough for the image of genius to be built, a period which became known as *Bardolatry*, a concept created by George Bernard Shaw (Shaw, 1910). The cult of Shakespeare had its apex when in 1840 Thomas Carlyle (Carlyle, 2011) treated him as the King of Poets and stated that "*Of this Shakspeare of ours, perhaps the opinion one sometimes hears a little idolatrously expressed is, in fact, the right one; I think the best judgment not of this country only, but of Europe at large, is slowly pointing to the conclusion, that Shakspeare is the chief of all Poets hitherto; the greatest intellect who, in our recorded world, has left record of himself in the way of Literature.*"(Carlyle, 2011, 85)

In the wake of the cult to William of Stratford, interest in his work was aroused everywhere. Such was the case for James Wilmot, a teacher from a small village 50 km from Stratford-Upon-Avon. According to James Shapiro (Shapiro, 2010), in 1785 James Wilmot began to investigate William's life. He went to Stratford looking for documents, papers, books or any other indication that could help him to trace *William's* profile as an author, but he found nothing. "*Wilmot gradually came to the conclusion that someone else, most likely Sir Francis Bacon, had written the plays*" as mentioned by Shapiro (Shapiro, 2010, 5). Wilmot never published his findings. It is assumed that he burned all his notes, but not before sharing his investigation with his friend James Cowell, who in turn shared the story in a presentation to the Ipswich Philosophical Society in 1805 (Shapiro, 2010). Both Wilmot and Cowell suggested that maybe Francis Bacon could hold the authorship of Shakespeare's plays.

After the Ipswich presentations, interest in the issue around the authorship was renewed. Despite the *Bardolatry*, once again the criticism manifested itself, this time with the poet Benjamin Disraeli (Ridley, 1995). In his novel *Venetia* de 1837, Disraeli puts into the mouth of the character *Cadurcis* the criticism about the authenticity of *William's* authorship and raised "*questions whether Shakespeare wrote half of the plays attributed to him or even a whole play*" (Ridley, 1995). In the year 1848 Joseph C. Hart was the first "*who asserted explicitly and unequivocally in print that Shakespeare did not write the works bearing his name. Hart claimed that Shakespeare was a "mere factotum of the theatre", a "vulgar and unlettered man hired to add obscene jokes to the plays of other writers*" (Wyman, 2003, 9). Smith draws attention to several aspects that could be taken as evidence that William was not the person whose education, knowledge of the circumstances of the time, and culture were sufficient to write the works that are attributed to Shakespeare (Smith,1857). These facts alluded to by Smith became, in fact, a kind of script for the search for evidence that has since been sought to justify the thesis that *William* did not write Shakespeare. Smith proposed

Francis Bacon as the real Shakespeare. Almost at the same time, still in 1857 Delia Bacon (Bacon, 1857) published a book entitled *The Philosophy of the Plays of Shakespeare Unfolded*, where she questioned William's authorship and also proposed Francis Bacon as the real pen writer behind Shakespeare.

The decade starting in 1850s, encounter the question about the authorship disseminated among the British intellectual circle, dominating the debate about the intellectual qualities of the real Shakespeare, with a large number of candidates being proposed by different personalities and William's life being closely scrutinized. Was *William* really incapable of writing Shakespeare? If that were true, then who was behind him? Who would be the ghost writer? These questions should be answered through a deep investigation into the William's life, with the aim of finding the reasons that would justify such an accusation. The issue of authorship was, therefore, focused on the search for full evidence that would bring clarity to the solution of such a dispute. The first candidate Francis Bacon was still far from unanimous. At the same time, two antagonistic groups had begun to organize themselves, 1) the group of supporters of *William*, those who defended the hypothesis that William of Stratford was really Shakespeare, and 2) the group of skeptics, those who sought an author to fit in a set of plays, paraphrasing Luigi Pirandello (Pirandello, 1921).

In the year 1920, John Thomas Looney (looney, 1920) published his bombastic book titled *Shakespeare Identified in Edward de Vere, the Seventeenth Earl of Oxford*. The book had a huge impact and captured the attention of the intellectuality even beyond Britain. In 1922 Looney founded *The Shakespeare Fellowship*, which aimed to coordinate public discussion on the subject. This movement had many supporters, including Sigmund Freud, who wrote a letter to Looney in support of De Vere as the author of Shakespeare (Waugman, 2017). Looney presented several reasons discrediting *William* as the author and showing the reasons why Edward De Vere should be considered the real writer behind Shakespeare. Looney started a movement, the Oxfordian movement, in search of the definitive proof for his thesis. This proof hasn't been found so far, but the bunch of evidences is now overwhelming.

In the following section, I will examine the issue of authorship from the perspective of the Mental Model. The literature produced by Shakespeare uses a sophisticated language that is only possible to acquire with years of study and reading. In addition, his works contain extensive references to the most diverse subjects, from horticulture to the English legal system, passing through the most complex situations of the Elizabethan court. Where would William have sought and learned so much information? What books and libraries would he have had access to? How would he have developed his skills, a way of thinking and seeing the world? For that is what the Mental Model we allude to is about.

3. Mental Models and the Authorship question

The idea of Mental Model originates from theories related to linguistic relativism developed since the 18th century. German thinkers Johann G. Hamann (and Johann G. von Herder (Beek, n/d) were the first to postulate that language has precedence and influence thought (Matallo Jr, 2023). This idea about language and thought reached their high point in 19th century with the publication of Wilhelm von Humboldt's book (Humboldt, 1988), where he stated that language shapes the Mind. Many others followed von Humboldt, both in philosophy and anthropology (Boas, 1940), consolidating finally the principle that language shapes the mind (Code, 1980: Snell, 1953) into the very known Whorf-Sapir hypothesis (Whorf, 1956).

Kenneth Craik took a step forward creating the concept of mental models (Craik, 1943). This concept has been widely discussed since then. Experiments have been conducted and empirical data collected. In an important collection of texts published in 2006, Professors Carsten Held, Markus Knauff, and Gottfried Vosgerau (Held, Knauff, Vosgerau, 2006) from various German institutions, showed many achievements in this area. It is worth mentioning two major advances made in the context of mental models that are related and can help us in approaching the theme of authorship. The first one was presented by Barbara Hemforth and Lars Konieczny (Hemforth & Konieczny, 2006), showing that conceptual representations and acquired knowledge play a central role in sentence processing. The second advance was made by studies conducted by Verena Gottschling (2006), showing that long-term memory plays an important role in the formation of mental models and, more than that, in shaping our behavior in everyday situations.

Characterizing our conceptual tool, we understand Mental Model as a representation, a way of conceiving the set of situations and occurrences of the outside world to which we are exposed. These representations condition our responses and these responses are based on knowledge, accumulated experiences, and long-term memories. These models are ultimately responsible for how we act socially, produce art or knowledge, or simply work to support our families. As Philip Johnson-Laird would say, "the mental model is an internal representation of a state of affairs in the external world" (Laird, 1992).

The next step in our characterization of Shakespeare Mental Model is to look for a description of his abilities. Alexander Pope in his Preface to the Complete Works of Shakespeare, offers a brilliant profile of the author. Taking the profile as a reference, I would say that Shakespeare Mental Model can be summarized as follows:

1. Deep understanding of emotions, motivations and human relationships and psychology.
2. Understanding the complexities derived from power relations, morality and human ambitions
3. Works influenced by a wide variety of sources, including Greek and Roman classics and English history
4. Deep understanding of the most immediate power relations in the Elizabethan court
5. Knowledge of different cultures, their manners and languages.
6. Precise command of the English language

These are the guiding criteria that should have shaped Shakespeare's mind. Does William comply with them? Did he develop these skills through reading, travel and experiences through an extensive network of relationships inside and outside Queen Elizabeth's court? That's what we'll see next.

4. William's profile

The first chapter of Smith's book (Smith, 1857) is entirely devoted to Shakespeare's biography. It took just twelve lines (yes, twelve lines) to say the following: "*William Shakespeare's is indeed a negative history. Of his life, all that we positively know is the period of his death. We do not know when he was born, nor when, nor where, he was educated. We do not know when, or where, he was married, nor when he came to*

London. We do not know when, where, or in what order, his plays were written or performed; nor when he left London. He died April 23rd, 1616" (Smith, 1857, 2). This is the entire biographical chapter and it is possible that at that time the amount of information relevant to profiling William was not much more than that. About William's work, not a single manuscript survived. No indication about a tutor or any kind of tutored activity. No indication of a library he used, and no indication whatsoever about him in his activity as an author, his routine in writing or reading. Nobody described or has ever mentioned his daily work as an author. There was no paper, notebook, or even books in his house. The only surviving documents are referred to contracts: the first is a loan and the second his will, in which he minutely names every item of property he owned, though he does not mention any books, plays, or anything else connected with his authorial activity (Smith, 1857).

It is said that William worked with his father, who was a sheep farmer and wool seller. It is also said that being in London and before launching himself as an actor, he worked taking care of the horses of those who came to the theater to watch the plays. He never left London excepting to come back to Stratford for visiting or living permanently at the end of his life. He didn't know other languages, even though some biographers mention that he had contact with Latin in the grammar school he attended between 7 and 12 years old. This is, however, doubtful considering the social conditions of Stratford-Upon-Avon at that time as mentioned early, with massive illiteracy in the community. How could someone with this profile, being a sheep farmer and horse caretaker, fulfill the qualities mentioned by Alexander Pope? How could a mind like William's be modeled without much reading and access to the kind of information Pope mentions? It is not easy to answer these questions, but the available biographical information tells us that such a mind could not be modeled, whether due to lack of information, lack of adequate language and the main activities he used to do in his day-to-day life.

In favor of William, Jonathan Bate suggests that he had access to Ben Jonson library and learned Latin and Greek at school from the age 8 to 12, and "*because of the power of memory and imagination—two of Shakespeare's greatest gifts—the mind does not obey the same rule of time as the entropic human body*" (Bate, 2009,). The reading of Shakespeare's plays allows the assumption that the author had great mental capacity (power of memory and imagination in Bate's words), but it does not authorize saying that William would be the owner of these capacities, especially in a situation of doubt such as the one that surrounds his biography. This is the foundation of the controversy over authorship. William's capabilities are not known, as he did not leave clear evidence about it, and hence the hypothesis that it is necessary to seek another person whose qualities are confirmed by the evidence to comply with the requirements.

Linguistic relativism (Matallo Jr, 2023) shows that language shapes the mind. The literature on the subject seems unequivocal. There are a number of studies on the subject and it seems that this case is no exception. When I say that language shapes the mind, we must accept that this statement has different levels of depth. We must also accept that there is no idea of determination in the language-mind relationship and I can mention as an example the Spanish writer Miguel de Cervantes, who did not have a refined education and is now considered the creator of the modern Spanish language. In the case of William of Stratford, it seems that it was not his background that limited his literary ability (I am here assuming that William is only a front man), but a combination of factors that led to this situation, factors that are still under discussion and could not be fully clarified so far.

So, how could William's mind be shaped for literary activity without considerable effort to overcome the limited conditions in which he lived? The answer to this question is that only an intense process of reading and studying would enable the acquisition of language, its adequate vocabulary and its formulas. Literature, drama and poetry have certain formulas for expressing ideas and feelings. Such resources need to be learned and manipulated with precision, otherwise they may not arouse the interest or identification of the reader with the play. In addition, all the information scattered throughout Shakespeare's work shows a great command of technical subjects, such as law, music, modern and ancient history, philosophy, and even falconry, gardening, and astronomy. Mastery of Latin, Greek, French, and Italian would have to be required to mold a mind like Shakespeare's. But did William's mind have what it takes to become Shakespeare's mind? Could a man without a biography, as mentioned by Gaston (2010) accomplish this feat just using intuition? Or would the ideal of the Shakespearean Mind be fulfilled by someone else?

After the release of Looney's book in 1920 and with the accumulation of evidence calling into question William's authorship, Edward De Vere was accredited as the most likely Shakespeare. This new candidate, in addition to placing Francis Bacon's candidacy in an unfavorable position, practically made the emergence of any other possible candidate unfeasible. Unlike William, De Vere had a tutor, had access to libraries, owned books and manuscripts, knew the court, had traveled to other countries, and spoke several languages. He was the opposite of William of Stratford. With regard to intellectual training, for instance, De Vere was guided by one of the most important intellectuals in England, Thomas Smith (Hughes, 2000), attending his library with more than 1000 books since he was 8 years old. He attended Cambridge, Oxford and law school. He later married the daughter of William Cecil, 1st Baron Burghley and chief adviser to Queen Elizabeth I during most of her reign. William Cecil was also a book collector and had a huge library for the time. In an inventory made in 1687, 3,645 books were counted (mentioned in <https://tudortimes.co.uk/people/william-cecil-bibliophile-map-collector>).

We assume that men with opposite biographies like William of Stratford and Edward De Vere, had their lives dedicated since childhood to essentially different activities. William was mainly engaged in business, first with his father and later as a food dealer and theater manager, and De Vere in intellectual and political activity, travel, poetry and literature. The Stratford man had a mental model focused on practical activities and businesses he had performed since his youth: Entrepreneurship and earning money. His main focus was to generate economic income. He didn't have his daily life sorted out. He needed resources to survive on a day-to-day basis. That simple. The fact that William became a business man was not fortuitous. It was derived from his activities to survive. There was no time to study and write. His creativity was directed towards business. He devoted himself extensively to commercial activities, specifically the buying and selling grains such as malt and barley, during a period marked by significant food shortages caused by climate-related crises. Research conducted by Jayne Archer (Archer, Thomas & Turley, 2015) indicates that William began his involvement with the grain trade as early as 1598 and experienced

Source:wikipedia

considerable financial success in this endeavor. In fact, William's wealth, which allowed him to acquire land and the largest house in Stratford-upon-Avon, did not primarily stem from his occupation as an actor and theater owner, but rather from his ventures as a grain merchant. And he was successful. So successful that the planning for his first tombstone showed William leaning on a sack of grain, suggesting that he was perhaps better known as a merchant than a man of

theater. The first drawing would have been made in 1649 and only later was it changed to an image where the purse is replaced by a cushion with William writing on it. The second image was made for the edition of Shakespeare's complete works published by Alexander Pope in 1725. Archer does not see contradiction in the two images, that is, in the two activities carried out by William, considering them complementary for someone who would have to feed his family. However, one wonders whether this might not have a close connection with William's prevailing mental model.

Edward De Vere was a different man with a different Mental Model. His mind was turned to political matters, as well as those related to human feelings. All those qualities mentioned by Alexander Pope in the *Preface* (Pope, 1725) that made Shakespeare the genius of literature. Where did he train and acquire this Mental Model? In the library initially, in his networking, and in the trips, he made in Europe. De Vere didn't have to work at anything to support himself. He didn't have to waste energy for a day-to-day job. He could dedicate himself, and he did, to study and reading. He had three tutors who directed him, learned Latin and Greek and mastered the English language at its highest level. Mostly important, he had full access to books in the libraries of his tutor Sir Thomas Smith and his father-in-law Sir Thomas Cecil. This was the basis of his Mental Model.

The situation was not different regarding to Francis Bacon. His father was a member of the court of Queen Elizabeth I and his mother was considered one of the most enlightened women in Europe. He possibly had a tutor or preceptor attending him at home, even though there is no mention to whom could have done it. He attended Trinity College, Oxford and studied law at the Gray Inn school. He had intense participation in politics (he was elected to the House of Commons) and English diplomacy. He excelled in philosophy and is considered one of the founders of empiricism. He met Ben Jonson, the leading poet of the day, who was also William's friend. Finally, a man of letters with a philosophical and literary background. He had a library with more than 1300 books and documents, and of these, 34 are considered direct sources of Shakespeare's works (<https://www.london.ac.uk/senate-house-library/our-collections/special-collections/printed-special-collections/francis-bacon-society-library>). Many scholars consider Bacon to be the man behind Shakespeare, as he has all the credentials to do so. As we would say, he had the conditions and the right mental model.

5. Tell Me What You've Read and I'll Tell You What You Can Write

We are dealing here with the formation of mental models through ideas and experience materialized in language, whether in the form of plays, poetry or scientific treatises. This process took place historically through written language. That means writing and reading. Access to books as a means of transmitting knowledge is a very characteristic practice of Western civilization that began with the Greeks. The Greek alphabet and writing were the most successful undertaking in history to standardize thought. We assume, as said before, the hypothesis that "language shapes the Mind" (Matallo Jr, 2023). For this reason, the title of this section and the article as a whole refers to books. "Tell me what you read and I'll tell you what you can write" it's not just an image to get attention. It is actually the center of the process for storing and transmitting knowledge of modern civilizations. Is a process that is in the center of the Western civilization since the foundation of Natural Philosophy by the Pre-Socratic philosophers (Matallo Jr, 2023).

The search for evidence to confirm Shakespeare's authorship occurred, from the beginning, through the tracking of sources that are assumed to be part of his work's content. They are cultural references that have their origin in the classics of Greek and Roman literature, as well as in existing literature and information already disseminated in the time. However, the tracking of sources is one of the elements that raises many questions. We don't know for sure which books the authors (William, De Vere) had access to and, even if they did, whether they read them seriously. Scholars hypothesize that having access means reading. If we accept this hypothesis, Shakespeare's plays result from a mind with extensive knowledge acquired through reading and language, as well as travel and contacts with the complex political situations in the court of Queen Elisabeth. It remains for us, therefore, to look for evidence to the possible access that William of Stratford and Edward De Vere, the strongest candidates for the place of Shakespeare, had to education and libraries in their time.

In Elizabethan times (1558-1603) education for the nobility and upper middle class began with tutoring exercised by a professional tutor from 4 to 8 years old. At age 8, formal education began in the educational system or Grammar Schools. The grammar school curriculum was centered on the study of Latin. Children also learned grammar, rhetoric, some mathematics and Latin literature. The study of Greek was not common, but it could be found in some schools. From the age 12, the luckiest began studies at Cambridge or Oxford and could, after that, study law at Gray's Inn for an additional two years period.

In the second half 16th century, there were no public libraries and access to books was quite restricted. Books were costly and one could not choose the language of publication. Hence the need to master Latin and Greek, the cultured languages of the time. As for reading, after the formal period of education that ended at age 12 for the most, only the children of the nobility or the upper class who had access to universities would continue to exercise systematic reading, having access to libraries in these higher schools. The others would have to buy or borrow the books if they wanted to continue reading and studying. Therefore, the time applied to systematic studies would be 10 years in total, taking into account tutoring (from 4 to 8 years) and university and law studies (an additional 2 years after university). For those who did not have access to a tutor and could not continue their studies after grammar school, the time dedicated to formal learning would be only 4 years.

Four years spent in grammar school is really too short a period to absorb all the classical culture. This could be quickly forgotten if the student in question had to dedicate his life after grammar school to hard manual work, as was the case with William. To summarize the matter: William was born in 1564 and was in primary school from 8 to 12 years old (1572 to 1576). In the whole period from 1576 to 1592 he supposedly worked with his father, married, and went to London. In fact, this time is called "lost years" and there is no reliable information about this period. The first months in London were also confusing. Some say he worked tending horses for audiences in front of the theater before starting to work on some smaller things, behind the stage first and then as an actor. We know nothing about access to libraries, books, or friends. His life actually begins in 1593.

Jonathan Bate makes a critical assumption for the whole argument in favor of the supposed intellectual capacity and mastery of knowledge necessary for the production of Shakespeare's works, that is, for William to fulfill the requirements mentioned previously regarding Mental Model. The sources of borrowed books would have been Ben Jonson, playwright and poet, and his friend, and Richard Field, who would become a printer in London and responsible for printing three poems attributed to Shakespeare (*Venus and Adonis*; *The rape of Lucrece*; *The Phoenix and the Turtle*). It is said that in 1611 Ben Jonson's library (McPherson, 1974) had more than 220 books, including Latin and Greek classics and that, possibly, William would have had access to these books. Bate's hypothesis is that William would have a super memory capable of registering ideas and contents with just a quick reading or even a fortuitous glance. Bate mentions that: "*where Jonson was a methodical reader, Shakespeare was an opportune one. He snapped up phrases and ideas from his reading, storing them in his capacious memory*" (Bate, 2009, 159). Richard Field would have printed some of the classics that William might have had access even before the launching of those books to the public, such as the 1595 edition of Plutarch's *Lives of Noble Greeks and Romans* and the 1589 Latin edition of Ovid's *Metamorphoses*. Field also printed Aristotle's translation of *Orlando Furioso*, the source for the main plot of *Much Ado About Nothing*, and perhaps had a copy of the 1587 edition of Holinshed's *Chronicles*, the key source for Shakespeare's English history plays (Bate, 2009).

Therefore, it can be inferred that William may have had access to the books in Jonson's library and some of the copies from Field's printing press. However, it is uncertain which books he actually read or the ideas and phrases he may have gleaned from his opportunistic reading, as Bate suggested. Additionally, it is worth noting that William did not receive formal tutoring or a comprehensive education beyond elementary school, which did not foster the systematic study necessary for developing a focused mental model for literary and poetic production.

As already mentioned, there are two likely candidates to fill Shakespeare's shoes. Whoever he was, he must have devoted himself intensely to the study of languages, having access to extensive literature available only in a few very specific private libraries, having traveled to Italy and elsewhere, as well as knowledge of the English court and its intricate relationships. In Appendix II, I present a summary of the brilliant work developed by Geoffrey Bullough (Bullough, 1966), which shows in great detail the influences Shakespeare had when writing his plays. Additionally, I used Kenneth Muir's book (Muir, 2005), also about Shakespeare's literary influences. Ninety-eight books were counted as references, which for the time was an expressive number. Many of the books mentioned as literary sources for Shakespeare were not in Jonson's. Therefore, William would have had access from another source, which seems unlikely.

The information about sources makes it possible to assert that whatever the man behind Shakespeare was, his mind was shaped by a wide and diverse literary and historical world. It seems clear that an opportunistic reading like "snapping up phrases and ideas and storing them in a capacious memory" does not seem feasible. It is assumed that mental models come with learning within a formative culture, that is, the person needs to immerse himself in a cultural environment, cultivate mental activity for a certain practice and, in the case of Shakespearean literature, absorb historical knowledge, courtly manners and behaviors, as well as the appropriate vocabulary. Creativity needs the appropriate inputs to function as such.

Finally, based on William's biography, we can state that the probability that he had access to the references mentioned in Annex II and had read them all is low. If we think that he should also have command of Greek and Latin and, still know the intricate plots of the court, it seems really unlikely. In the other hand, it does not seem very plausible to expect such spontaneous mental development, as Pope said in his *Preface* (Pope, 1725), from a man accustomed to business and who needed to solve the daily problems of survival. What is known about his biography shows, therefore, that his Mental Model was more focused on business than on literary production. The other two possible candidates for Shakespeare have a biography more in line with the required Mental Model, which we alluded to in section 3. It is not our intension place to look for an author for Shakespeare here, but to show that the use of Mental Models can be promising in literary analysis or, at least, as an additional resource in this polemic that has lasted for 400 years.

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Appendix I

Sources: Bullough, Geoffrey (1966). Narrative and dramatic sources of Shakespeare, 8 volumes, Routledge and Kegan Paul, NY.

Muir, Kenneth (2005). The Sources of Shakespeare's plays. Routledge.

Plays	Date	Sources
The comedy of Errors	1591	Plautus (c.254-184 BC). <i>Menaechmi</i> (performed 1592 with English translation by William Warner, printed 1595) Plautus (c.254-184 BC). <i>Amphitryon</i> (Latin) George Gascoigne (1542-77). <i>Supposes</i> (performed 1566, published 1573, 1587. Translation of Italian drama, <i>I suppositi</i> (1509).
The Taming of the Shrew	1593	<i>Thrésor d'Histoires Admirables et Mémorables</i> of S. Goulart Anonymous ballad. <i>A Merry Jest of a Shrewede and Curste Wyfe</i> (printed 1550) Gascoigne, George (1542-77). <i>Supposes</i> (performed 1566, published 1573, 1587. Translation of Italian drama, <i>I suppositi</i> (1509) Anonymous. <i>The Taming of a Shrew</i> (1594)
Venus and Adonis	1593	Ovid (43 BC – 18 AC). <i>Metamorphoses</i> (Arthur Golding's translation in 1567)
The Rape of Lucrece	1594	Ovid (43 BC- AD18). <i>Fasti</i> Book 2. (Latin version) Titus Livius (59BC-AD17). <i>Ab urbe condita libri</i> Book 1. (Latin) Painter, William (1540-94). <i>The Palace of Pleasure</i> (1566-7) Geoffrey Chaucer (c.1340-1400). <i>The Legend of Good Women</i> (c. 1386)
Two Gentlemen of Verona	1590	Giovanni Boccaccio (1313-75). <i>Decameron</i> 10th day, the story of "Titus and Gisippus" Elyot, Thomas (c.1490-1546). <i>The Boke named the Governour</i> (1531) Montemayor, Jorge de (c.1521-61). <i>Diana Enamorada</i> (1542, English translation in 1582. publication in 1598) the story of "Felix and Felismena" Anonymous. <i>The History of Felix and Philomena</i> (the record of the performance in 1585) Brooke, Arthur (?-1563). <i>The Tragical History of Romeus and Juliet</i> (English translation in 1562) Lyly, John (c.1554-1606). <i>Euphues: The Anatomy of Wit</i> (1578)
Romeo and Juliet		Brooke, Arthur (?-1563). <i>The Tragical History of Romeus and Juliet</i> (English translation in 1562)
A Midsummer's Night Dream		Plutarch (c.46-120). <i>Theseus and Hippolyta in Lives of the Noble Grecians and Romans</i> (Thomas North's translation in 1579) Chaucer, Geoffrey (c.1340-1400). <i>The Canterbury Tales</i> (1400) The story of "Pyramus and Thisbe" and the name of Titania. Ovid (43 BC- AD18). <i>Metamorphoses</i> (Arthur Golding's English translation in 1567) Anonymous. <i>Huon of Bordeau</i> , a 13th-century

		French adventure tale translated by Lord Berners (1534)
Edward III	1590 2	Froissart, Jean (c.1337-1410). <i>Chroniques</i> (c.1495) (John Bouchier's English translation in 1523-5) Painter, William (1540-94). <i>The Palace of Pleasure</i> (1566-7) Holinshed, Raphael (c. 1528-c. 1580). <i>The Chronicles of England, Scotland and Ireland</i> . (2nd ed., 1587)
Henry VI (1,2,3)	1590 – 1592	Hall, Edward (1498-1547). <i>The Union of the Two Noble and Illustre Families of Lancaster and York</i> (3rd. ed., 1550) Holinshed, Raphael (c. 1528-c. 1580). <i>The Chronicles of England, Scotland and Ireland</i> . (2nd ed., 1587) Fabyan, Robert (?-1513). <i>New Chronicles of England and France</i> (1516) Grafton, Richard (c.1512-c.1572). <i>A Chronicle at Large of History of the Affayres of England</i> (1516) Hardyng, John (1378-c.1465). <i>The Chrocicle of John Hardyng</i> (1543) Foxye, John (1516-87). <i>The Book of Martyrs</i> (4th ed., 1583) William Baldwin ed. <i>The Mirror for Magistrates</i> (1559 ed.) Edmund Spenser (c.1552-99). <i>The Faerie Queene</i> (1590) Brooke, Arthur (?-1563). <i>The Tragical History of Romeus and Juliet</i> (English translation in 1562) - Kyd, Thomas (1558-94) <i>The Spanish Tragedy</i> (1588-9) and <i>Soliman and Perseda</i> (1590)
Titus Andronicus		Anonymous. <i>Titus Andronicus</i> Ovid (43 BC- AD18). <i>Metamorphoses</i> (Arthur Golding's English translation in 1567) Seneca, Lucius Annaeus (4 BC-65 AD). <i>Thyestes</i> (English translation in 1560)
Richard III	1592	Holinshed, Raphael (c. 1528-c. 1580). <i>The Chronicles of England, Scotland and Ireland</i> . (2nd ed., 1587) Hall, Edward (1498-1547). <i>The Union of the Two Noble and Illustre Families of Lancaster and York</i> (1587 edition) More, Thomas. <i>History of King Richard the Thirde</i> . (1543) William Baldwin ed. <i>The Mirror for Magistrates</i> (1559 ed.)
<u>Love's Labour's Lost</u>	1590	No sources mentioned.
Richard II	1595	Hall, Edward (1498-1547). <i>The Union of the Two Noble and Illustre Families of Lancaster and York</i> (3rd. ed., 1550) Holinshed, Raphael (c. 1528-c. 1580). <i>The Chronicles of England, Scotland and Ireland</i> . (2nd ed., 1587) Anonymous. <i>Thomas of Woodstock</i> (c. 1592) Froissart, Jean (c.1337-1410). <i>Chroniques</i> (1495?) (John Bouchier's English translation in 1523-5)

		William Baldwin ed. <i>The Mirror for Magistrates</i> (1559 ed.) Daniel, Samuel (c.1562-1619). <i>The Civil Wars between the Two Houses of Lancaster and York</i> (1595-1609)
King John		Anonymous. <i>The Troublesome Raigne of John King of England</i> (1591?) Holinshed, Raphael (c. 1528-c. 1580). <i>The Chronicles of England, Scotland and Ireland</i> . (2nd ed., 1587) Fuxe, John (1516-87). <i>The Book of Martyrs</i> (4th ed., 1583)
The Merchant of Venice	1596	Fiorentino, Giovanni (14th-century). <i>Il Pecorone</i> (1578) <i>Gesta Romanorum</i> (1340, translation by Richard Robinson, 1595 ed) a Lost English play <u>The Jew</u> Marlowe, Christopher (1564-93). <i>The Jew of Malta</i> (c. 1589) Munday, Anthony (1560 – 1633). <i>Zelauto: The Fountaine of Fame</i> . (1580)
The Merry Wives of Windsor	1597	Fiorentino, Giovanni (14th-century). <i>Il Pecorone</i> (1578) Ovid (43 BC- AD18). <i>Metamorphoses</i> (Arthur Golding's English translation in 1567) Lyly, John (c.1554-1606). <i>Endimion</i> (1588)
Much Ado About Nothing	1598	Ludovico Ariosto (1474-1533). <i>Orlando Furioso</i> (1516) (The English translation by John Harrington in 1591) Bandello, Matteo (1485-1561). <i>Novelle</i> (1554-73). Edmund Spenser (c.1552-1599). <i>The Faerie Queene</i> (1590) Francois de Belleforest (1530-83). <i>Histoires Tragiques</i> (1568) Book 3 Whetstone, George (1544 – 1587). <i>The Roke of Regard</i> (1576) Castiglione, Baldassare (1478-1529). <i>The Book of the Courtier</i> (1528)
Henry V	1599	Holinshed, Raphael (c. 1528-c. 1580). <i>The Chronicles of England, Scotland and Ireland</i> . (2nd ed., 1587) Anonymous. <i>The Famous Victories of Henry the Fifth</i> (c. 1586) Robert Fabyan (?-1513). <i>New Chronicles of England and France</i> (1516) Daniel, Samuel (c.1562-1619). <i>The Civil Wars between the Two Houses of Lancaster and York</i> (1595-1609)
Julius Caesar	1599	Plutarch (c.46-120). <i>Lives of the Noble Grecians and Romans</i> (Thomas North's English translation in 1579) Appian [Appianos] (2nd century). <i>Civil Wars</i> (English translation in 1578) Anonymous. <i>The Tragedy of Caesar and Pompey, or Caesar's Revenge</i> (c. 1595)
As You Like It	1599	Lodge, Thomas (c.1557-1625). <u>Rosalynde</u> (1590)
Hamlet	1600	Kyd, Thomas (1558-94). <i>Ur-Hamlet</i> (c. 1589)

		Francois de Belleforest (1530-1583). <i>Histories Tragiques</i> Book 5 (1570)
Twelfth Night		Riche, Barnabe (c.1540-1617). <i>Farewell to Militarie Profession</i> (1581) the story of " <u>Apolonius and Silla</u> " Bandello, Matteo (1485-1561) <i>Novelle</i> (1554-73)
The Phoenix and the Turtle	1601	Chester, Robert (?). <i>Love's Martyr where The Phoenix and the Turtle appears</i> (1601) Ovid (43 BC- AD18). <i>Amores</i> . Matthew Roydon's elegy in <i>The Phoenix Nest</i> Chaucer, Geoffrey (c.1340-1400). <i>The Pralement of Foules</i>
Troilus and Cressida	1602	Homer (c. 900.BC). <i>Iliad</i> (English translation in 1598 by George Chapman) Chaucer, Geoffrey (c.1340-1400). <i>Troilus and Cresseide</i> (c. 1385) Caxton, William (c.1421-91). <i>Recuyell of the Historyes of Troye</i> (1475, 5th ed. 1596) Lydgate, John (c.1370-1449). <i>The Troy Book</i> (1412-20, 1555 ed)
A Lover's Complaint	1604	Samuel Daniel (c.1562-1619). <i>The Complaint of Rosamond</i> (1592) Edmund Spenser (c.1552-99). <i>Complaints</i> (1591)
Measure for Measure	1604	Geroge Whetstone (c.1544-87). <i>Promos and Cassandra</i> (1578) Cinthio, Giovanni Battista Giraldi (1504-73). <i>Hecatommiti</i> (1565. No English translations have found, therefore, Shakespeare probably read it either in Italian or French.) Cinthio, Giovanni Battista Giraldi (1504-73) <i>Epietia</i> (1583. No English translations have found, therefore, Shakespeare probably read it either in Italian or French) Barnabe Riche (c.1540-1617). <i>The Adventures of Brusanus, prince of Hungaria</i> (1592)
Othello	1604	Cinthio, Giovanni Battista Giraldi (1504-73). <i>Hecatommiti</i> (1565. No English translations have found, therefore, Shakespeare probably read it either in Italian or French) Book 2, 7th story of "Disdemona and the Moor" Pliny, the Elder (23-79). <i>Naturalia Historia</i> (Philemon Holland's translation in 1601) Africanus, Leo. <i>A Geographical History of Africa</i> (English translation by John Pory, 1600)
All's Well That Ends Well	1605	Painter, William (1540-94). <i>The Palace of Pleasure</i> (1566-7)
Timon of Athens	1605	Plutarch (c.46-120). <i>Lives of the Noble Grecians and Romans</i> (Thomas North's translation in 1579) Lucian (c. 120-180). <i>Timon, the Misanthrope</i> (No English translation which Shakespeare could use is found.) John Lyly (c.1554-1606). <i>Campaspe</i> (c. 1584) Anonymous. <i>Timon</i> . (c. 1602)
King Lear	1606	Anonymous. <i>The True Chronicle History of King Leir</i> (c. 1590) Holinshed, Raphael (c. 1528-c. 1580). <i>The Chronicles of England, Scotland and Ireland</i> . (2nd ed.,

		1587) Sidney, Philip (1554-86). <i>The Arcadia</i> (1590) Spenser, Edmund (c.1552-99). <i>The Faerie Queene</i> (1590)
Macbeth	1606	Holinshed, Raphael (c. 1528-c. 1580). <i>The Chronicles of England, Scotland and Ireland</i> . (2nd ed., 1587) Seneca, Lucius Annaeus (4BC. - AD 65). <i>Hercules Furens and Agamemnon</i> (English translation in 1565)
Antony and Cleopatra	1607	Plutarch (c.46-120). <i>Lives of the Noble Grecians and Romans</i> (Thomas North's translation in 1579) Appian [Appianos] (2nd century). <i>Civil Wars</i> (English translation in 1578) Daniel, Samuel (c.1562-1619). <i>The Tragedy of Cleopatra</i> (c. 1594)
Pericles	1607	Gower, John (c. 1330-1408) <i>Confessio Amantis</i> . (1554 ed) which was from the medieval collection of Latin tales, <i>Gesta Romanorum</i> (c. 1340) Twine, Lurence (?). <i>The patterne of Painefull Adventures</i> (1576) Sidney, Philip (1554-86). <i>The Arcadia</i> (1590)
Coriolanus	1608	Plutarch (c.46-120). <i>Lives of the Noble Grecians and Romans</i> (Thomas North's translation in 1579) Livy, Titus or Livy (59BC-AD17). <i>Ab Urbe Condita Libri</i> (Philemon Holland's English translation as <i>The Romane Historie</i> in 1600.) Camden, William (1551-1623). <i>Remaines of Greater Worke Concerning Brittain</i> (1605) Averell, William A <i>Marvailous Combat of Contrarieties</i>
Cymbeline	1609	Holinshed, Raphael (c. 1528-c. 1580). <i>The Chronicles of England, Scotland and Ireland</i> . (2nd ed., 1587) William Baldwin ed). <i>The Mirror for Magistrates</i> (1559 ed.) Anonymous. <i>Frederyke of Jennen</i> 3rd ed., (1560) Anonymous. <i>The Rare Triumphs of Love and Fortune</i> (1589) Boccaccio, Giovanni (1313-75). <i>Decameron 10th day</i>
The Winter's Tale	1609	Robert Greene (c.1558-92). <i>Pandosto</i> (1588) Ovid (43 BC- AD18). <i>Metamorphoses</i> (Arthur Golding's English translation in 1567)
The Tempest	1611	No particular reference
Henry VIII	1613	Holinshed, Raphael (c. 1528-c. 1580). <i>The Chronicles of England, Scotland and Ireland</i> . (2nd ed., 1587) Foxe, John (1516-87). <i>The Book of Martyrs</i> (4th ed., 1583)
Two Noble Kinsmen	1613	Chaucer, Geoffrey (c. 1340-1400). <i>The Canterbury Tales</i> (c.1482) Plutarch (c. 46-120). <i>Lives of the Noble Grecians and Romans</i> (Thomas North's translation in 1579) Beaumont, Francis (c. 1584-1616). <i>the Masque of</i>

Appendix II

1. Africanus, Leo. *A Geographical History of Africa* (English translation by John Pory, 1600)
2. Anonymous ballad. *A Merry Jest of a Shrewede and Curste Wyfe* (printed 1550)
3. Anonymous. *The Tragedy of Caesar and Pompey, or Caesar's Revenge* (c. 1595)
4. Anonymous. *Titus Andronicus*
5. Anonymous. *Frederyke of Jennen* 3rd ed., (1560)
6. Anonymous. *The Famous Victories of Henry the Fifth* (c. 1586)
7. Anonymous. *The History of Felix and Philomena* (the record of the performance in 1585)
8. Anonymous. *The Rare Triumphs of Love and Fortune* (1589)
9. Anonymous. *The Taming of a Shrew* (1594)
10. Anonymous. *The Troublesome Raigne of John King of England* (1591?)
11. Anonymous. *The True Chronicle History of King Leir* (c. 1590)
12. Anonymous. *Thomas of Woodstock* (c. 1592)
13. Anonymous. *Timon*. (c. 1602)
14. Appian [Appianos] (2nd century). *Civil Wars* (English translation in 1578)
15. Averell, William. *A Marvailous Combat of Contrarities*
16. Bandello, Matteo (1485-1561) *Novelle* (1554-73)
17. Barnabe Riche (c.1540-1617). *The Adventures of Brusanus, prince of Hungaria* (1592)
18. Beaumont, Francis (c. 1584-1616). *the Masque of the Inner Temple and Gray's Inn* (1613)
19. Boccaccio, Giovanni (1313-75). *Decameron 10th day*.
20. Brooke, Arthur (?-1563). *The Tragical History of Romeus and Juliet* (English translation in 1562)
21. Brooke, Arthur (?-1563). *The Tragical History of Romeus and Juliet* (English translation in 1562)
22. Camden, William (1551-1623). *Remaines of Greater Worke Concerning Brittain* (1605)
23. Castiglione, Baldassare (1478-1529). *The Book of the Courtier*.(1528)
24. Caxton, William (c.1421-91). *Recuyell of the Historyes of Troye* (1475, 5th ed. 1596)
25. Chaucer, Geoffrey (c. 1340-1400). *The Canterbury Tales* (c.1482)
26. Chaucer, Geoffrey (c.1340-1400). *The Legend of Good Women* (c. 1386)
27. Chaucer, Geoffrey (c.1340-1400). *The Pralement of Foules*
28. Chaucer, Geoffrey (c.1340-1400). *Troilus and Criseyde* (c. 1385)
29. Chester, Robert (?). *Love's Martyr where [The Phoenix and the Turtle](#) appears* (1601)
30. Cinthio, Giovanni Battista Giral di (1504-73) *Epitia* (1583. No English translations have found, therefore, Shakespeare probably read it either in Italian or French)
31. Cinthio, Giovanni Battista Giral di (1504-73). *Hecatommithi* (1565). No English translation has been found, therefore, Shakespeare probably read it either in Italian or French.
32. Daniel, Samuel (c.1562-1619). *The Civil Wars between the Two Houses of Lancaster and York* (1595-1609)

33. Daniel, Samuel (c.1562-1619). *The Tragedy of Cleopatra* (c. 1594)
34. Edmund Spenser (c.1552-1599). *The Faerie Queene* (1590)
35. Edmund Spenser (c.1552-99). *Complaints* (1591)
36. Elyot, Thomas (c.1490-1546). *The Boke named the Governour*(1531)
37. Fabyan, Robert (?-1513). *New Chronicles of England and France* (1516)
38. Fiorentino, Giovanni (14th-century). *Il Pecorone* (1578)
39. Foxe, John (1516-87). *The Book of Martyrs* (4th ed., 1583)
40. Foxe, John (1516-87). *The Book of Martyrs* (4th ed., 1583)
41. François de Belleforest (1530-1583). *Histories Tragiques* Book 5 (1570)
42. Froissart, Jean (c.1337-1410). *Chroniques* (1495?) (John Bourchier's English translation in 1523-5)
43. Gascoigne, George (1542-77). *Supposes* (performed 1566, published 1573, 1587. Translation of Italian drama , *I suppositi* (1509)
44. *Gesta Romanorum* (1340, translation by Richard Robinson, 1595 ed)
45. Gower, John (c. 1330-1408) *Confessio Amantis*. (1554 ed) which was from the medieval collection of Latin tales, *Gesta Romanorum* (c. 1340)
46. Whetstone, George (c.1544-87). *Promos and Cassandra* (1578)
47. Grafton, Richard (c.1512-c.1572). *A Chronicle at Large of History of the Affayres of England* (1516)
48. Hall, Edward (1498-1547). *The Union of the Two Noble and Illustre Families of Lancaster and York* (3rd. ed., 1550)
49. Hall, Edward (1498-1547). *The Union of the Two Noble and Illustre Families of Lancaster and York* (3rd. ed., 1550)
50. Hardyng, John (1378-c.1465). *The Chrocicle of John Hardyng* (1543)
51. Holinshed, Raphael (c. 1528-c. 1580). *The Chronicles of England, Scotland and Ireland*. (2nd ed., 1587)
52. Homer (c. 900.BC). *Iliad* (English translation in 1598 by George Chapman)
53. John Lyly (c.1554-1606). *Campaspe* (c. 1584)
54. Kyd, Thomas (1558-94) *The Spanish Tragedy*_(1588-9) and *Soliman and Perseda* (1590)
55. Kyd, Thomas (1558-94). *Ur-Hamlet* (c. 1589)
56. Livius, Titus or Livy (59BC-AD17). *Ab Urbe Condita Libri* (Philemon Holland's English translation as *The Romane Historie* in 1600.)
57. Lodge, Thomas (c.1557-1625). *Rosalynde* (1590)
58. Lucian (c. 120-180). *Timon, the Misanthrope* (No English translation which Shakespeare could use is found.)
59. Ludovico Ariosto (1474-1533). *Orlando Furioso* (1516) (The English translation by John Harington in 1591)
60. Lydgate, John (c.1370-1449). *The Troy Book* (1412-20, 1555 ed)
61. Lyly, John (c.1554-1606). *Endimion* (1588)
62. Lyly, John (c.1554-1606). *Euphues: The Anatomy of Wit* (1578)
63. Marlowe, Christopher (1564-93). *The Jew of Malta* (c. 1589)
64. Matthew Roydon's elegy in *The Phoenix Nest*
65. Montemayor, Jorge de (c.1521-61). *Diana Enamorada* (1542, English translation in 1582. publication in 1598) the story of "Felix and Felismena"
66. More, Thomas. *History of King Richard the Thirde*. (1543)
67. Munday, Anthony (1560 – 1633). *Zelauto: The Fountaine of Fame*. (1580)
68. Ovid (43 BC – 18 AC). *Metamorphoses* (Arthur Golding's translation in 1567)
69. Ovid (43 BC- AD18). *Amores* .
70. Ovid (43 BC- AD18). *Fasti* Book 2. (Latian version)
71. Ovid (43 BC- AD18). *Metamorphoses* (Arthur Golding's English translation in 1567)

72. Anonymous. *Huon of Bordeau*, a 13th-century French adventure tale translated by Lord Berners (1534)
 73. Ovid (43 BC- AD18). *Metamorphoses* (Arthur Golding's English translation in 1567)
 74. Painter, William (1540-94). *The Palace of Pleasure* (1566-7)
 75. Plautus (c.254-184 BC). *Amphitryon* (Latin)
 76. Plautus (c.254-184 BC). *Menaechmi* (performed 1592 with English translation by William Warner, printed 1595)
 77. Pliny, the Elder (23-79). *Naturalia Historia* (Philemon Holland's translation in 1601)
 78. Plutarch (c. 46-120). *Lives of the Noble Grecians and Romans* (Thomas North's translation in 1579)
 79. Plutarch (c.46-120). *Lives of the Noble Grecians and Romans* (Thomas North's translation in 1579)
 80. Riche, Barnabe (1581?). *Farewell to Militarie Profession*, the story of "Apolonius and Silla"
 81. Robert Fabyan 1516?). *New Chronicles of England and France*
 82. Robert Greene (1588). *Pandosto* (1588)
 83. Samuel Daniel (1592?). *The Complaint of Rosamond*
 84. Seneca, Lucius Annaeus (4 BC-65 AD). *Thyestes* (English translation in 1560)
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